

Prostate cancer patient cases (diagnosis images and clinical data) for the testing of AI models

ID: 846a5512-8dfc-4bbd-afe7-fd16bf7b44f0

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/846a5512-8dfc-4bbd-afe7-fd16bf7b44f0/details>

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Contact info.: None

Studies count: 288

Subjects count: 288

Age range: Between 48 years and 86 years

Sex: Male

Body part(s): PROSTATE, ARM, PELVIS, ABDOMEN, SKULL, Pelvis^Masculin, HEAD, PANCREAS, LUMBAR SPINE, Unknown

Modality: MR, DX